

A Study of Relational Crises in Leslie Silko's *Ceremony*

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Abstract:

Ceremony (1977) by Leslie Marmon Silko is a significant work in Native American literature. The novel narrates the story of Tayo, a mixed-blood Laguna Pueblo soldier who returns home after World War II, suffering from trauma, loneliness, and confusion about his identity. Tayo, the protagonist's family relationships play an important role in his struggles and his recovery. This study is an attempt to investigate that how does Silko present family relationships as complex influencing element that cause emotional pain, cultural disconnection, and ultimate healing. Through the characters Auntie, Josiah, and Grandma in the narrative, Silko aims to show the effects of family expectations, traditions, and generational values on Tayo's identity and mental state. The study argues, although family relationships have first deepened Tayo's crisis, it help later in reconnecting him with culture and in moving toward spiritual healing.

Keywords: Kinship, Crises, Healing, Culture, Traditions.

Introduction:

The novel, *Ceremony* (1977) is a major work in Native American literature. This body of literature often deals with themes such as identity, cultural survival, and the impact of colonization on Indigenous communities. Silko's *Ceremony* narrates a story of Tayo, a young man of mixed Native American and white ancestry who returns to the Laguna Pueblo reservation after serving in World War II. After the war, Tayo suffers from psychological trauma and feels disconnected from his community and surroundings. His struggles are not only the result of his war experiences but are also closely connected to the complex family relationships that has influenced his upbringing and identity. At one side, some complex family relationships create emotional crises and communal conflict but some of them also offer support and cultural continuity on the other side. The concept of family in contemporary Native

American culture was deeply rooted in their ancestral beliefs and tribal heritage. The author shows Tayo's family as a representation of contemporary Native American life which is central to the novel. This research article examines family relationships represented in *Ceremony* and its role in Tayo's identity crisis and recovery. The present study has been carried out to accomplish the following objectives:

1. To analyse the different forms of relational crises in the contemporary Native American family.
2. To investigate post World War II sufferings of Native American people.
3. To highlight the importance of family and community in surviving cultural heritage and regaining lost identity.

The Importance of Family in Native American Cultural Context:

Native American literature often emphasizes the importance of cultural heritage and collective memory. Many works highlight the role of oral storytelling traditions in preserving history and identity within the community. These narratives reflect the deep connection between cultures, tradition, and communal values (Velie and Lee 45). In many Native American communities, family structures extend beyond the nuclear family and include a wider network of relatives and community members. These extended relationships are important in maintaining culture, tradition, and collective identity. In *Ceremony*, Silko family reflects this culture by presenting complex family structure with members carrying cultural knowledge and spiritual traditions. The novel also highlights the severe effects of colonization on the Native American communities. It was the Europeans' arrival and their attempts of landholding of natives which disturbed traditional social structures based on cultural beliefs. Silko has represented the characters of old and new generation to underline the importance of carrying cultural heritage in Native American communities even in different challenges. As noted by critic Arnold Krupat in his book, *The Voice in the Margin: Native American Literature and the Canon*, Native American literature often focuses on the challenge of preserving cultural identity under the pressure of external influences (45).

Thus, Tayo's crisis are not just of individual level but of a cultural and communal level. He occupies an uncertain position within the Laguna Pueblo community, where issues of identity and belonging are closely connected to cultural heritage, because of his mixed Native American and white ancestry. In the novel, Silko presents two different approaches towards the

Native American beliefs through the representations of characters as Auntie wants to maintain reputation in white society by keeping traditional values aside whereas Tayo's grandmother strongly believes that only the cultural continuity can provide them identity and spiritual happiness. Therefore, the expectations and attitudes of Tayo's family members play an important role in shaping his self-perception and his search for acceptance.

Tayo's Family Background and Identity Crises:

Tayo's early life, as portrayed in the novel, is affected by unstable family relations and social judgements. Laura, Tayo's mother who rejects Laguna Pueblo life and wants to enjoy independent life. She becomes marginalized within her community due to this approach and her relation with white man. Thus, Tayo as a child of Native American woman and white man could neither get pure parental love nor proper communal identity. Tayo's father leaves the family in trouble and Laura lives a miserable life. Laura doesn't take responsibility of Tayo and leaves him to Auntie, her sister. After living lonely, dislocated life, in severe hardships and alcoholism, she dies at young age.

After Laura's decline, Tayo is taken in by his Auntie, who raises him within the family but never fully accepts him with affection. Auntie is strongly concerned about the family's reputation and feels ashamed of Laura's actions. Because of this, she treats Tayo with a sense of duty rather than genuine warmth. So, Tayo's early life is of uncertainty and emotional crisis. As a child of mixed blood he could neither get place in community as Native American nor as white in White community. While growing up in such an environment, Tayo develops feelings of rejection and inferiority. His mixed racial identity is another reason for this. These feelings are further

strengthened with the subtle discrimination he experiences within the community and racial prejudice he encounters while serving in the war. Through these experiences, Silko demonstrates how complicated family relationships can contribute to personal conflict and an ongoing struggle for identity.

War Trauma and the Cultural Alienation of Tayo:

Silko's *Ceremony* depicts how Tayo's personal struggles are intensified by the traumatic experiences that he faces during World War II. During the war, Tayo witnesses violence, suffering, and the deaths of fellow soldiers including his cousin Rocky. These events deeply affect his mental and emotional well-being, leaving him with feelings of guilt and confusion. The loss of Rocky, who represented hope and success within the family, increases Tayo's sense of responsibility and grief. As a result, the war becomes a significant deeply moving event that dig out his psychological crisis.

After returning to the Laguna Pueblo reservation, Tayo continues to suffer from nightmares, emotional detachment, and physical weakness. Tayo's illness was more than just physical and that is why the treatment of European doctors could not give any result. His suffering was psychological, spiritual, communal which could have been cured through traditional healing process in which whole ecosystem become a part of the process. The novel highlights that Native Americans were fully been operated by the colonizers for war and other purposes of colonizers. Through Tayo's experiences, Silko highlights the wider historical impact of war on Native American communities. Many indigenous soldiers joined the war expecting recognition and equality, but that became nightmare for them with experiences of social discrimination and marginalization there.

As pointed out by Hongyan Du in his research article, the novel demonstrates that Native Americans veterans cannot return with normal life and behaviour. They become addicted to alcohol and lost good memories of their culture and indigenous heritage (806). This amalgamation of war trauma and cultural discontinuation strengthens Tayo's struggle, reflecting the broader challenges faced by Native Americans who must traverse between rich traditional cultural values and the pressures of modern American society. Mr. J. G. Ravi Kumar rightly points out in his research article, '*Ceremonies of Culture a Study of Leslie Marmon Silko*' that Silko has portrayed some of the ways that created guilt in Native American Indians; guilt of losing beloved ones and of losing cultural identity under the influence of European culture (3).

Family Relationships, Crises and Regaining Identity:

1. Auntie: Social Expectations and Emotional Distance:

Auntie is one of the most complex family figures in the novel. Apparently, she raises Tayo and provides him with a home. However, her actions are mostly driven by social expectations rather than real love. Auntie cares deeply about the family's reputation in the Laguna Pueblo community. She has constant concern that Laura's past will bring shame to the household. Auntie shows reluctance when Grandma suggests to take Tayo to medicine man to heal him. Her concern was gossips about the Laura and deeds will restart in community. Even such cases were a day to day matter in contemporary Native American communities, Auntie's concern was that it should not happen in their family. In this case, Silko demonstrates Auntie's approach as,

“Oh, I don't know, Mama. You know how they are. You know what people will say if

we ask for a medicine man to help him. Someone will say it's not right, they'll say, 'Don't do it. He's not full blood anyway.' (30)

Auntie often keeps Tayo emotionally at a distance because his presence reminds her history. Her attitude highlights the conflict between personal kindness and social pressure. While she does her job as a caretaker, her failure to fully accept Tayo deepens his feelings of rejection. Auntie takes more care of her own son Rocky and ignores the Tayo at the same. But she pretends other that she equally loves both. Auntie's treatment to Tayo is clearly portrayed by Silko in following words:

It was private understanding between the two of them. When Josiah or Old Grandma or Robert was there, the agreement was suspended and she pretended to treat him the same as she treated Rocky, but they both know it was only temporary. (61)

Scholars have pointed out that Auntie's character represents the weight of cultural expectations in traditional communities (Allen 120). Through Auntie, the author shows how family relationships can unintentionally lead to emotional struggles. The need to maintain social respectability often blocks real communication and understanding within the family. To Ellie Croot in her article, Silko portrays Auntie as outlining of contemporary Native Americans' tribal and cultural beliefs which they want to continue in the surroundings of white too (3). To Mr. J. G. Ravi Kumar, Auntie doesn't believe in clan system of Native Americans which aims to keep whole family together. He further states that the kinship structures of natives, to some extent, was changed due to the arrival of Europeans and influence of Christianity (105).

2. Josiah: Cultural Guidance and Emotional Support:

In contrast to Auntie's strict and distant attitude, her husband Josiah serves as a source of emotional warmth and cultural guidance for Tayo. Josiah shows compassion and understanding, offering him the acceptance that he rarely receives from other family members. He teaches Tayo about Laguna traditions, the importance of respecting the land, and the deep spiritual connection between human beings and nature. These lessons play a crucial role in shaping Tayo's understanding of cultural identity and belonging. Josiah's supportive relationship with Tayo highlights the positive role that family members can play in strengthening identity and emotional stability. Unlike Auntie, he does not judge Tayo for his mixed blood heritage but instead recognizes his potential and encourages him to embrace his cultural roots. However, Josiah's death during the war becomes a major turning point in Tayo's life. The loss of this guiding figure deepens Tayo's grief and sense of isolation, leaving him without the emotional support that once helped him cope with his internal struggles.

3. Grandma: Cultural Wisdom and Spiritual Healing:

Another significant family figure in the novel is Tayo's grandmother, who represents the continuity of cultural traditions and spiritual wisdom within the Laguna Pueblo community. Unlike Auntie, Grandma approaches Tayo's suffering with empathy and understanding. She strongly believes in traditional healing practices and recognizes that Tayo's psychological distress cannot be fully treated through Western medical methods. Instead, she encourages him to seek help from a Native healer and to participate in traditional ceremonies that restore balance and harmony. Her beliefs reflect the important role of elders in indigenous cultures as protectors of

cultural memory and spiritual knowledge. She strongly favours the ceremonial healing process of medicine man to Tayo even after Auntie's initial rejection to it by considering possible gossips regarding Tayo's mixed blood identity in community. Grandma firmly conveys her beliefs to Auntie as "*He is my grandson. If I send for old Ku'oosh, he'll come. Let them talk if they want to. Why do you care what they say? Let them talk. By planting time they'll forget*" (31). Through Grandma's character, Silko highlights the value of intergenerational relationships in preserving cultural identity. Grandma's faith in traditional healing ultimately guides Tayo toward recovery and cultural reconnection, demonstrating that family support can play a crucial role in overcoming emotional and cultural crises.

4. *Betonie: Traditional Healing and Cultural Restoration:*

Ceremony accentuates the role of traditional healers in Tayo's journey toward recuperation. These figures represent the spiritual and cultural knowledge that has been preserved within Native American communities for generations. Unlike Western medical doctors who focus mainly on physical symptoms, medicine men or healers address the deeper spiritual and emotional imbalance experienced by individuals. In the novel, Tayo's suffering is understood not only as psychological trauma caused by war but also as a disturbance in the harmony between the individual, the community, and the natural world. The medicine men therefore guide Tayo through traditional ceremonies that aim to restore balance and reconnect him with his cultural roots.

One of the important healers in the story is Betonie, a Navajo healer who plays a crucial role in Tayo's recovery. Betonie believes that ceremonies must adapt to changing times because the world itself is constantly evolving. His approach to healing combines traditional indigenous knowledge with an awareness of

contemporary realities. Through rituals and storytelling, Betonie helps Tayo in understanding that his experiences are part of a larger cultural and historical struggle faced by Native American communities. Betonie encourages Tayo to continue the healing process by reconnecting with the land, his community, and his cultural traditions. Through the character of the medicine man, Silko highlights the significance of indigenous spiritual practices and shows that true healing requires the restoration of cultural identity and spiritual balance. She has condemned the whites for the exploitation of natives and has glorified the ecosystem of Native American land where they can get healed by surviving with environment. Betonie's words, "*They keep us on the north side of the railroad tracks, next to the river and their dump. Where none of them want to live....They don't understand. We know these hills and we are comfortable here.*" (108), clearly underline that Native Americans were deeply connected with their land and environment which could strengthen their protest to survive cultural heritage. Here in Tayo's case, his reconnection with his own community, land and culture was required which the Medicine man Betonie did by applying scalp and sand painting ceremony.

Joseph Coloumbe points out in his book, *Reading Native American Literature* that Silko distinguished the American Indian beliefs and Christianity. She highlighted through the dialogues and emotional sharing of characters that Christian influence crushed the single clan system of Native Americans and the effects of it are shown through the sufferings of Tayo (72). On other hand, Silko supports the clan system of Native Americans in which provides same consciousness and specific identity which Tayo also gets at the end of novel by accepting the clan. She recalls "*when the people shared a single clan name and ... the people shared the same consciousness*" (*Ceremony*, 68).

Conclusion:

Silko's *Ceremony* offers a nuanced exploration of how family relationships influence personal crises within the context of Native American cultural experience. Tayo's struggles with identity, trauma, and alienation are closely tied to the complex dynamics of his family environment. Through characters such as Auntie, Josiah, and Grandma, Silko demonstrates the varied ways in which family members can shape an individual's emotional and cultural development. Some relationships, like that with Auntie, heighten tension and reinforce feelings of rejection, while others, particularly Josiah and Grandma, provide guidance, wisdom, and cultural continuity. The novel shows that family functions not only as a source of conflict but also as a foundation for healing. Tayo gradually overcomes his personal struggles and regains a sense of belonging by reconnecting with cultural traditions, spiritual practices, and the wisdom of elders. Silko's narrative thus underscores the vital role of family, community, and cultural heritage in addressing the psychological, social, and cultural challenges faced by Indigenous peoples in the modern world. As the novel comprises the different aspects of Native American life and culture, there is remarkable scope for analysing it through the lens of ecocriticism and ecofeminism. It can be also interpreted with the aspects such as Native American oral traditions, Myths, storytelling and healing ceremonies.

References:

1. Silko, Leslie Marmon. *Ceremony*. Penguin Books, 1977.
2. Velie, Alan R., and A. Robert Lee, editors. *Native American Literature: An Anthology*. University of Oklahoma Press, 1997.
3. Krupat, Arnold. *The Voice in the Margin: Native American Literature and the Canon*. University of California Press, 1989.
4. Allen, Paula Gunn. *The Sacred Hoop: Recovering the Feminine in American Indian Traditions*. Beacon Press, 1986.
5. Coulombe, Joseph L. *Reading Native American Literature*. Routledge, 2011

Research Articles:

1. Du, Hongyan. "From the Invisible to the Visible: An Analysis of Tayo's Return in *Ceremony*." *Advances in Social Science, Education and Humanities Research*, vol. 496, Atlantis Press, 2020, pp. 805–809.
2. Ravi Kumar, J. G. "Ceremonies of Culture: A Study of Leslie Marmon Silko." *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Approach and Studies*, vol. 2, no. 1, Jan.–Feb. 2015, pp. 100–106.
3. Croots, Ellie. "'Every Day the Loss Was with Them': Disentangling the Complexities of Trauma in *Ceremony*." *Fields: Journal of Huddersfield Student Research*, University of Huddersfield, 2017, pp. 1-7